

Clinical Evaluation of Treatment Adopted for Proximal Tibial Epiphyseal Fractures in Children Aged Below 14 Years in a Tertiary Care HospitalNagesh Muddamsetti¹, Y G Raghava Naidu², Saya Venkateswara Prasad³, Battu Maheswara Reddy⁴¹Assistant Professor of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh²Assistant Professor of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh³Associate Professor of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh⁴Assistant Professor of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:

Background: Proximal Tibial epiphyseal fractures are rare and they make up less than 01% of all epiphyseal (growth plate) separations. These fractures require significant force and occur in a region with intrinsic stability due to the surrounding structures; collateral ligaments and fibular buttress. Aim of the Study: To evaluate the operative treatment for children with proximal Tibial epiphyseal fractures, with the objectives of enumerating the Indications for surgery, surgical techniques adopted, Advantages and disadvantages, Possible complications and Overall results.

Materials: A prospective case series study was conducted between December 2022 and January 2024 at Al Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh. 23 children with proximal Tibial epiphyseal fractures were included. Treatment method adopted was surgical intervention with various fixation methods.

Results: The mean operative time was 59.25±17.45 minutes, with a range from 36 to 93 minutes. The mean intra-operative blood loss was 36.25 mL (range: 23.15 to 36.50 mL). Fixation methods used were 'K' wires in epiphyseal group-75% of the children; cannulated screws were used in remaining 25% of the children. In the tubercle group, fixation was more varied: 50% had 4.5 mm cannulated screws and 25% had a combination of 4.5 mm cannulated screws and tension band 25% had K-wires.

Conclusion: Proximal tibial epiphyseal fractures are uncommon but potentially serious due to the risk of limb-threatening complications. Close monitoring of neurovascular status is crucial to detect any acute or delayed complications. There is a low tolerance for failure in maintaining the reduction after fixation, especially when using K-wires, which may require supplementary fixation to ensure the best outcome.

Keywords: Kirchner wire, Fracture epiphysis, tibia, children and proximal Tibial injuries.

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Introduction

Fractures of the proximal Tibial epiphysis require a significant amount of force, and therefore, these injuries account for less than 1% of all epiphyseal separations. [1] The proximal Tibial epiphysis has intrinsic varus–valgus and side-to-side translational stability because of the collateral ligaments and the lateral fibular buttress. [2] In adolescents, the most critical features of proximal Tibial epiphyseal fractures are proximity to the popliteal artery and the possible development of compartment syndrome. [3] The rapid advancements in science and technology and the popularization of various modern means of transportation have greatly improved liv-

ing standards. [4] However, these improvements have also increased the incidence of trauma caused by various energies. [5] The incidence of fractures in children, who tend to show poor awareness of self-protection, has been consistently increasing, so that epiphyseal and epiphyseal plate fractures are common bone injuries in childhood. [6] Epiphyseal injuries accounted for 17.9% of all pediatric fractures in Japan. [7] The Salter-Harris classification is the most commonly used system for categorizing epiphyseal fractures in children. [8] The epiphyseal plate in children is a layer of weak cartilage tissue responsible for the longitudinal and lateral growth

of long bones. [9] It lacks blood supply and has poor regenerative ability. [10] Therefore, improper treatment of epiphyseal fractures can have serious consequences, including bone bridge formation and premature epiphyseal plate closure, potentially causing shortened limbs and/or angular deformities, which can result in lifelong disabilities. [11] Epidemiological findings can be expected to provide a scientific basis for improving the quality of life for children with epiphyseal fractures, formulating health education policies, and reducing the economic burden associated with these fractures. [12] Although potentially problematic regarding an apophyseal fracture of the tibial tubercle, the metaphyseal overhang of the tubercle can provide anterior-posterior translational support. [13] An avulsion fracture of the tibial tuberosity is uncommon, accounting for less than 01% of all epiphyseal injuries and approximately 03% of all proximal Tibial fractures. [14] Most fractures concerning the proximal Tibial epiphysis result in anterior, anterolateral, and anteromedial epiphysis displacement relative to the metaphysis caused by the anatomic stability. [15] In the rare fracture with posterior displacement, the epiphysis and tubercle apophysis are displaced as a single unit. [16] The tibial tuberosity acts as an effective block, making posterior displacement rare. In such injuries, the fracture usually propagates along the epiphyseal extension beneath the tibial tuberosity, so that the proximal tibial epiphysis and tuberosity are displaced as a single unit. [17] Fractures of the proximal tibial metaphysis usually occur in children aged 3–6 years and may be complete or greenstick. [18] In contrast, the tibial tubercle fracture is most commonly sustained by adolescents; the most critical features of proximal tibial epiphyseal fractures are proximity to the popliteal artery and possible development of compartment syndrome. In the present study evaluation of the operative treatment for children with proximal Tibial epiphyseal fractures, with the objectives of enumerating the Indications for surgery, surgical techniques adopted, Advantages and disadvantages, Possible complications and overall results were analysed.

Materials:

From December 2022 and January 2024, a prospective case series study was performed at Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Kurnool. The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee in the Orthopedic Department of the Hospital. A total of 23 children with proximal epiphyseal fractures were admitted and treated.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients aged up to 14 years were included. Patients who are skeletally immature were included. Patients with open fractures were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients aged above 15 years were excluded. Patients with fractures more than 3 weeks duration were excluded. Children with pathologic fractures were excluded.

Patient-Criteria: 23 patients; out of whom 12 male and 11 female children with tibial epiphyseal fractures were classified into two groups: the epiphyseal group consisting of 12 children (52.17%) and the tubercle group 11 (47.82%) children were separated. Salter-Harris (19) (S.H) type 1 accounted for approximately 26.08%, S.H type 3 accounted for approximately 26.08%, S.H type 2 accounted for approximately 26.08%, and S.H type 4 accounted for approximately 21.765% in the epiphyseal group. In the tubercle group, type III A accounted for approximately 47.84%, type III B accounted for approximately 26.08%, and type II C accounted for approximately 26.08%. The mean age was 12.50 ± 2.7 years for the epiphyseal group and 13.15 ± 1.5 years for the tubercle group. The injuries mostly occurred during jumping and sport activities. At initial presentation, no patient had compartment syndrome. Sequelae following acute tibial tubercle avulsion fractures are rare in the reported series. There were only six children (26.08%) with pre-existing osteo-chondritis dissecans (OSD) among the 23 acute injury cases.

Operative-Management: (a) Anesthesia: General anesthesia was used in all patients. Prophylactic antibiotics were administered with induction of anesthesia. The operating room table used was radiolucent, preferably without metallic side bars. Positioning aids included an assistant for counter-traction. Fluoroscopy was positioned opposite the surgeon and the back table. Equipment included a C-arm, smooth pins, unopened trays for open reduction, and trays for open reduction including a cannulated compression screw system (4.0–6.5 mm sizes available). A non-sterile tourniquet was used, though it may not need to be inflated unless surgery was converted to open reduction.

(b) Operative Technique: Closed reduction and percutaneous pinning of proximal tibial epiphyseal fractures Surgical Steps: Closed reduction of the fracture was performed under C-arm guidance. The technique of reduction varied depending on the direction of the displacement of the proximal fracture fragment. Reduction was best achieved under image intensifier control. The surgeon applied longitudinal traction to the leg, while an assistant stabilized the thigh. For hyperextension injuries, traction followed by flexion of the distal fragment usually achieved reduction. Salter-Harris types I and II valgus injuries were reduced by longitudinal traction followed by application of a gentle varus stress. If the fracture was deemed stable, a long-leg cast was applied with the knee in extension, and varus moulding was used. If the fracture was unstable, smooth, crossed trans-

physeal pins could be used to stabilize the reduction. In type II fractures with a large lateral fragment, the fracture may be stabilized with pins or screws across the metaphyseal portion of the fracture. Types I and II varus injuries were managed similarly, except that after closed reduction, valgus moulding was applied to the long-leg cast.

Fixation Options: Option 1: Smooth cross-pinning pin placement (Salter-Harris type 1 and 2). Option 2: Guide pin placement that does not cross the epiphysis in the metaphyseal fragment (Salter-Harris type 2) followed by drill placement of the proximal cortex with a cannulated system compression screw. Option 3: Smooth pin placement that does not cross the epiphysis, but crosses the apophysis in the tibial tubercle fragment was used.

This smooth pin can serve as a guide for compression screw placement if desired. For smooth pin placement, the pins were bent and cut to be pulled at 4–6 weeks postoperatively.

For cannulated screws, stab incisions were closed with sutures. A dressing was applied, and a long-leg cast was placed in 30° of knee flexion. Open reduction internal fixation (ORIF) of proximal-tibial-epiphyseal-fractures: The preoperative plan for open reduction and internal fixation followed the steps outlined in the closed reduction and percutaneous pinning section, with two exceptions: it was used for Salter-Harris type III and IV epiphyseal injuries, plus types IIB, IIIA, IIIB, and IV tibial tuberosity avulsion fractures. Additionally, associated quadriceps or patellar

tendon avulsions should be repaired to restore the extensor mechanism. A long medial or lateral parapatellar incision was made, depending on the location of the fracture. Soft tissues were dissected down to the fracture, and the fracture was exposed widely both medially and laterally into the joint until the epiphyseal fracture was visible. The epiphyseal fragment was elevated. Debris was washed out, and interposed periosteum was removed from between the fragments. The fracture was then anatomically reduced. Joint congruity and apposition of the fragments at the peripheral extra-articular margins were checked. Smooth K-wires were inserted through the reduced fragment from medial and lateral aspects to the metaphysis, crossing each other distal to the growth plate. If there was a long metaphyseal fragment, it was fixed using cancellous screws. A tension band was applied after tendon repair. The wound was closed in layers with a suction drain, and an above-the-knee cast was applied.

Postoperative-Care: Patients were made non-weight bearing and generally immobilized in a long-leg or cylinder cast for 4–6 weeks. Rehabilitation focused on range-of-motion exercises and progressive strengthening of the extensor mechanism. Full motion and quadriceps strength were required for a return to sports, usually not sooner than 12 weeks.

Results

The nature of fractures in the two groups of upper Tibial injuries in children was classified as Epiphyseal and Tubercle type and tabled in Table 1.

Table 1: Showing the types fractures observed under the two categories of Epiphyseal fractures and Tubercle injuries (n-23)

Type of fracture- Number	Types of fractures/injuries
Epiphyseal Injuries-12	1. Irreducible type I and II fractures. 2. Fractures associated with vascular injury. 3. Displaced Type III or IV Fracture
Tubercle injuries-11	1. Types IIB, IIIA, IIIB, and IV tibial tuberosity avulsion fractures. 2. Associated quadriceps or patellar tendon avulsions

The mean operative time was 54.15±3.10 minutes (range: 25–90 minutes; SD: 22.45), for Epiphyseal injuries surgery and 57.15±1.10, for Tubercle Injuries. The average intra-operative blood loss of 25 mL (range: 20–30 ml) for Epiphyseal injuries surgery and 28.5 mL for, Tubercle Injuries.

The fixation method varied based on the fracture type. In the epiphyseal group, K-wires were used in approximately (09) 75% of cases, while cannulated screws (4.5 mm) were used in about (03) 25%. In the tubercle group, 05 (45.45%) of cases were treated with cannulated screws (4.5 mm), 03

(27.27%) with a combination of cannulated screws (4.5 mm) and a tension band, and 03 (27.27%) with K-wires. Arthrotomy was performed in 03 (27.27%) of the epiphyseal group, while patellar tendon repair was necessary in 03 (27.27%) of the tubercle group.

The follow-up period ranged from 3 to 24 months, with a mean of 11.06 ± 7.80 months for Epiphyseal injuries and 12.50± 3.65 months for the Tubercle Injuries. Fracture union occurred in all patients, with a mean time of 5 ± 1 week (range: 4–6 weeks).

Table 2: Showing the types of surgical methods used, post-operative signs and healing time in the study (n-23)

Observation	Epiphyseal Injuries-12	Tubercle injuries-11	P value
Mean operative time	54.15±3.10	57.15±1.10	0.001
Blood loss	25mL	28.5 mL	
K Wire	09	03	
Cannulated screw	03	05	
Patellar tendon repair	--	03	
Arthrotomy	03	--	
Mean follow up time	11.06 ± 7.80 months	12.50± 3.65	0.001
Mean Fracture union time	5 ± 1 week	5 ± 1 week	0.001

Clinical union was confirmed by the absence of tenderness and satisfactory knee joint function, including a full range of motion. Among the 20 patients, two complications were recorded in four patients: two required hardware removal due to prominence, and two (10%) developed pin-tract infections, which were managed with antibiotics and daily saline dressing, leading to good outcomes. Other complications reported in the literature, such as malunion, nonunion, fracture through the fixation device, sephalous nerve neuronal, prominent tubercle, pain on squatting, numbness below the tuberosity, posterior cruciate ligament laxity, leg-length discrepancy, or deep venous thrombosis, were not observed in our cohort (see Tables 2–5).

Discussion

Avulsion fractures of the tibial tubercle, particularly those extending to the tibial epiphysis, are rare occurrences. [19] These injuries can compromise the vascular supply of the limb, making vigilant monitoring of limb perfusion essential. The avulsion force typically occurs while the quadriceps femoris is contracted, leading to the separation of the anterior portion of the proximal tibial epiphysis (the tibial tubercle), [20]. The closure of the proximal tibial epiphysis starts posteriorly, with the anterior part fusing last.

This pattern explains why these fractures are more common in adolescents and young adults between the ages of 14 and 18, as the anterior portion of the proximal tibial epiphysis remains more vulnerable, making them prone to type 1 or type 2 Salter–Harris injuries. [21, 22 and 23] The Ogden classification, which modifies the earlier Watson–Jones classification, is widely used to categorize these injuries. Ryu and Debenhams [24] introduced a type 4 classification to describe an avulsion fracture of the entire proximal tibial epiphysis.

However, we do not consider this a tibial tubercle injury but rather a complete separation of the proximal tibial epiphysis. [25] McKoy and Stanitsk [26] further proposed a type 5 classification, combining Ogden's type 3B with a Salter–Harris type IV fracture of the proximal tibia, creating a 'Y' configuration. [27] Gowda and colleagues [28] suggested

that osteochondritis dessicans (OSD) could be a predisposing factor for acute tibial tubercle injuries, noting that seven of nine patients with pre-existing OSD from a series of 14 acute injuries had contralateral knee involvement, but no similar injuries occurred on the affected side. All of the cited authors recommend open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) as the primary treatment method for displaced tibial tubercle fractures. The method of osteosynthesis varies depending on the patient's age, from using a tension band in younger children to employing screws in older patients [29]. Achieving accurate positioning of the fracture fragments, ensuring complete articular surface congruence, is critical.

In present case series study, the fractures were stabilized using two cannulated screws inserted percutaneously in parallel, a method deemed fully sufficient for fracture management. Generally, the fracture pattern and degree of displacement are key factors that determine the need for surgical intervention and the overall outcome. While various fixation techniques or constructs can be used, achieving anatomic, rigid fixation is crucial. This is particularly important in growing skeletons because proper restoration of epiphyseal and articular anatomy helps avoid growth disturbances and degenerative joint disease. [30]

Tibial tubercle fractures represent high-energy injuries and carry the risk of severe complications, including compartment syndrome and vascular compromise. Intra-articular involvement is often overlooked in plain radiography, which significantly underestimates the severity of the injury. [31]

Conclusion

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of operative management for children with proximal tibial epiphyseal fractures, with satisfactory clinical and radiological outcomes and no major complications. Although rare, fractures of the proximal tibial epiphysis in this young population can lead to limb-threatening complications, making constant monitoring of neurovascular status critical for detecting acute and delayed compromise. A cautious approach should be taken when using supplementary fixation, such as K-wires, due to the difficulty

in maintaining reduction and the risk of poor outcomes if the reduction is lost.

The primary goal of surgical treatment for tibial tubercle fractures is to restore the extensor mechanism and joint surface, along with all its associated components. Early recognition and treatment generally lead to good results.

The limitations of this study include the small sample size and the absence of a control group treated with open plating. A larger, randomized controlled trial is needed in the future to confirm the outcomes observed in this study.

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